

FAIR Data Management Plan v1

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List Of Abbreviations

AES	Advanced Encryption Standard
AI	Artificial Intelligence
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
EEA	European Economic Area
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GCP	Good Clinical Practice
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
ICT	Information Communication Technologies
ID	Identification Document
PCLS	Precision-Cut Lung Slices
PII	Personally Identifiable Information
PU	Public
SEN	Sensitive
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
TLS	Transport Layer Security
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the document

This document provides an analysis of the main elements of the data management policy that will be used by SynAir-G project consortium with regards to all the datasets that will be generated by the project during its implementation. It describes the data management life cycle for all data sets that will be collected, processed or generated by the research project. It includes:

- what data will be collected, processed or generated
- what methodology and/or standards will be applied
- how this data will be exploited and/or shared/made accessible for verification and reuse
- the handling of research data during & after the project

In this regard, it is a document outlining how research data will be handled during the said research project, and even after the project is completed, describing the different type of data, the methodology and standards that will be followed, whether and how this data will be shared and/or made open, and how it will be curated and preserved. Furthermore, the various aspects of making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR), as well as security, ethical, and privacy-related aspects, are presented.

The described data management policy reflects the current state of consortium understanding regarding data management and is consistent with the exploitation and protection of the project results. It needs to be noted that at the time of the submission of the current deliverable, the SynAir-G architecture was not finalised. In that sense, updates on the datasets and the storage provisions may be needed. The DMP is a living document updated and reviewed according to the project developments and the Horizon Europe guidelines. The final version will be submitted as a deliverable (D7.10) in Month 42.

Table 1 Mapping of the deliverable content versus the Task description

SynAir-G GA Component Title	SynAir-G GA Component Outline	Respective Document Section(s)	Justification
Task 7.5 – FAIR Data Management and Open-Source Contributions	Development of the Data Management Plan, which will include information related to the types of data and metadata the project will generate and collect	Chapter 2	Chapter 2 includes all the datasets that are collected/generated during the project on WP level as well as the respective project results/deliverables.
	the standards that will be used to represent the data during the project.	Chapter 3	Chapter 3 includes guidelines on how the datasets need to be represented in order to follow the FAIR principles.

	The DMP will set management procedures to protect sensitive data collected as a result of project activities.	Chapter 3, 4, 5	Chapter 3 describes the procedures that need to be followed in order to ensure FAIR principles are respected, Chapter 4 provides an overview of the processes related to the security of the data while Chapter 5 includes the procedures in order to protect the personal data.
	... a core part of this task is to develop a public repository in ZENODO to share the generated scientific data	Chapter 6	Open access of the research outputs including the ZENODO repository are discussed in Chapter 6.
	and to ensure the respect of FAIR Guiding Principles to allow user-friendly access to information about exposures, sources, and risk factors.	Chapter 3, 5,	Chapter 3 describes the procedures that need to be followed in order to ensure FAIR principles are respected and the means in order to ease access to data, Chapter 5 includes the relevant processes that ensure the ethical and data protection rules are followed in a convenient manner for the researchers and the research subjects.

1.2. Definitions

Table 2 List of definitions

List of Definitions	
Datasets	A structured collection of data generally associated with a unique body of work.
Personal Data	Any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'). An identifiable natural person is one who can be identified directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person. Information can fall under the category of personal data for example if it can be linked to an identifiable person through accessing a register.
Sensitive Data	Classified information that must be protected and is inaccessible to outside parties unless specifically granted permission. Sensitive data is regarded as private information or data for the protection of interests in business, individual rights, organizations, R&D, political, economics, security of the EU or member states, etc. Sensitive data, or special category data, according to GDPR is any data that reveals a subject's information.

Anonymisation	The process of removing personal identifiers, both direct and indirect, that may lead to an individual being identified. An individual may be directly identified from their name, address, postcode, telephone number, photograph or image, or some other unique personal characteristic. An individual may be indirectly identifiable when certain information is linked together with other sources of information, including, their place of work, job title, salary, their postcode or even the fact that they have a particular diagnosis or condition. Once data is truly anonymised and individuals are no longer identifiable, the data will not fall within the scope of the GDPR and it becomes easier to use.
Pseudonymization	A data management and de-identification procedure by which personally identifiable information fields within a data record are replaced by one or more artificial identifiers, or pseudonyms. The use of pseudonymization in personal data may reduce the risk associated with data management and help controllers and processors to comply with their data protection obligations. Pseudonymization does not imply a complete anonymization or complete dissociation of the data or the impossibility of reversion of the same. This is because there is always the possibility of identifying the party concerned through additional information. Unlike anonymization, it is considered as personal data by GDPR
Metadata	Information about datasets stored in a repository/database template. For example, an image may require metadata that describe how large the picture is, the colour depth, the image resolution, when the image was created, and other data. A text document's metadata may contain information about how long the document is, who the author is, when the document was written, and a short summary of the document.
Profiling	Any form of automated processing of personal data consisting of the use of personal data to evaluate certain personal aspects relating to a natural person, in particular to analyse or predict aspects concerning that natural person's performance at work, economic situation, health, personal preferences, interests, reliability, behaviour, location or movements.
Primary Data	Primary data is a type of data that is collected by researchers directly from main sources through interviews, surveys, experiments, etc.
Privacy by Design	Is the principle that privacy should be promoted as a default setting of every new ICT system and be built into systems from the design stage

1.3. Structure of the document

The document is structured as follows:

- Chapter 2 provides an overview of the data lifecycle and a summary of the data collected and generated throughout the project.
- Chapter 3 presents the guidelines in order the project to follow the FAIR principles, as well as specific metrics to measure the performance.
- Chapter 4 discusses the data security aspects.

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- Chapter 5 outlines the ethical aspects of the different project activities as well as the personal data protection measures.
- Chapter 6 explains how the research outputs should be handled.
- Chapter 7 concludes the deliverable.

2. Data Summary

The first step for the preparation of a DMP, is the definition of the data collection concepts and data purposes as they relate to the project's work-breakdown structure. In this context, the purpose of this section is mainly to define the means of data collection, the format of data collected as well as their origin and any other information deemed necessary.

The input information is collected through a questionnaire circulated to all SynAir-G partners (available in Annex I).

Following the input received, the data related to the SynAir-G project activities have been identified as follows:

- Data related to the project research activities including the health data from wearables, samples provided by research participants during the experiments and a gamified app, necessary for the real-life multipollutant scenario implementation.
- Data related to experiments outcomes.
- Project related documentation, reporting and management files,
- Other documents relating to the SynAir-G wide dissemination and exploitation activities (events, workshops etc.)
- open-source data collected from publicly available sources

The structure of chapter 2 complies with the FAIR data management template of the EC¹ (DMP component). In this regard, what follows is a first a description of the data lifecycle and then detailed description of the data produced or processed for each of the SynAir- G WPs.

2.1. Data Lifecycle

In this first section, the entire data lifecycle taking place in project is described and analysed. This means that the different stages at which data will be generated, managed or processed during the project execution as well as after its closure, will be taken into account.

In the next paragraphs, the analysis of the data lifecycle as well as the means to control, manage and report the related data is presented. In each of the following paragraphs, specific guidelines have been created for ensuring the data management control and compliance. Figure 1 demonstrates the indicative typical data lifecycle, without excluding any alternative data flows if needed during the project execution.

¹ See Section 3

Figure 1 Data Lifecycle

2.1.1. Creation/Collection

The first step in the data lifecycle is the data creation and/or collection, as it relates to the various data generated within the project activities as analysed in detail in section 2.4. This step mainly refers to the data creation by each of the data owners as well as to the collection of these data in order to be further processed by the SynAir-G Consortium for the execution of the project activities as described in the DoA. It needs to be highlighted that these data, need to be collected in a structured manner and appropriate formats and layouts to enable their processing by the other project components/modules.

To ensure compliance with the applicable rules, specific guidelines have been created, as presented in the table below:

Topic	Guideline -Means to ensure compliance
Format	Compliance with existing standards of data exchange
Availability and Readability	Whole package of data available, non-corruption, whole percentage collected (e.g. verifiable by hash functions)
Fit for Use	Data follow data compliancy for proper processing and review
Consistency and Completeness	Data is consistent and complete for the intended purpose
Relation	Data following a precise relation to their purpose

2.1.2. Processing and Analysis

The second stage is concerned with the actual data processing by the numerous data processors, who are the project partners and will have access to the data for distribution in accordance with the needs and results of the project. In this context, we need to make sure that the right partners can process data quickly. Every step toward data verification, organization, transformation, integration, and extraction for the intended application

is included in this stage. Data analysis entails all procedures/actions carried out on the real data to characterize existing facts, recognize patterns, create data explanations, etc. This stage works closely with the previous one.

To ensure compliance with the applicable rules, specific guidelines have been created, as presented in the table below:

Topic	Guideline -Means to ensure compliance
Data logic	Data can be and are processed following a concise logic and approach
Organization and Utility	Suitable content organization of data under processing
Validation	Ensuring that the data under processing are correct and relevant
Aggregation	Whenever multiple data need to be aggregated ensure that this is done in a concise approach
Transformation	Transformation of data to the proper format(s) for processing
Calibration	Calibration of data for their intended purpose

2.1.3. Data Publication and utilization

The term data publication refers to the ability for sharing these data openly while utilization includes the necessary steps that the project needs to perform internally to be able for such data sharing. This suggests that the data should be independent to ensure that the transfer can be carried out using an automated or manual method. In order to secure private data and the integrity of the data itself, it is important to make sure that the Data is shared with the necessary regulating mechanisms at every step of the project. As far as the use of metadata is concerned and to ensure that they can be easily accessible, the current stage as well as the next one (data storage and archiving) are closely related (as another feature of the FAIR data treatment-see section 3).

To ensure compliance with the applicable rules, specific guidelines have been created, as presented in the table below:

Topic	Guideline -Means to ensure compliance
Means-independent	Transferring of the data in a means-independent approach
Security (a)	Data stored in a secure server

2.1.4. Data Storage, Archiving and Re-Use

When it comes to data access, sharing, storage, archiving (including search capabilities), and re-use, the storage and archiving stages are also crucial. The data's updated state, which ensures that no newer versions exist, is a crucial consideration in this step (unless is clearly indicated). This should also include measures to prevent

unintentional data loss, corruption, and access. Data reusability, which falls under the FAIR data handling, is also closely related to data storage and archiving.

In order to ensure compliance with the applicable rules, specific guidelines have been created, as presented in the table below:

Topic	Guideline -Means to ensure compliance
Up to date	Ensuring that the stored Data is up to date for the specific purpose and no later version exists
Meta Data	Existence of metadata in stored files
Security (b)	Access control provided
Security (c)	Server is considered as safe enough (TLS connection protocol)
Bandwidth	Control of server bandwidth
Expiration	Properly setting expiration dates for all data after which the data will be deleted

2.2 Purpose of the Data Collection/Generation and its relation to project objectives

SynAir-G aims to reveal and quantify synergistic interactions between different pollutants affecting health, from mechanisms to real life, focusing on the school setting. Within the project lifespan, a comprehensive and responsive multipollutant monitoring system will be developed, advancing environmentally friendly interventions, and disseminating the generated knowledge to relevant stakeholders in accessible and actionable formats.

To achieve these objectives, SynAir-G will construct and deploy novel and improved sensors of chemical and biological (allergens, microbes) pollutants. These will be tested in a real-world setting, in participating schools of 6 countries around Europe and eventually combined into a multisensing platform. In the same setting, pollutants will be linked to their sources and two eco-friendly air-purifying devices will be assessed. Health outcome data will be obtained from children using a gamified app and prospective monitoring, respecting privacy. Highly susceptible children, such as those with allergy or asthma, will act as sentinels to increase sensitivity of the system, that will be able to provide stratified (susceptibility-specific) alerts. Explainable AI will support the near-real time analysis and response. In parallel, cell and mouse models will evaluate the mechanisms and complex dose-responses of the synergistic parameters.

SynAir-G will thus provide data on air pollutants and their sources, a comprehensive and personalized user-friendly solution to monitoring indoor air quality, and proposals for possible interventions and an improved regulatory framework, robustly supporting the Zero Pollution Action Plan.

2.3. Types and Formats of the collected/generated data

During the start of the project, the consortium identified the following data categories:

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- qualitative and quantitative research data (experimental outcomes, sensor data, participants' health data, etc)
- administrative data (participants' details, communications, etc.);
- open-source data collected from publicly available sources (environmental, socioeconomic, literature etc);
- publications and dissemination data related to open peer-reviewed publications, interviews, reports, proceedings.

In this scope, the general categories of the data that are going to be available into the scope of the SynAir-G project are the following.

- Information about the consortium: Personal information about the consortium members, such as name, surname, email, phone number etc., will be handled and stored in the Microsoft Share Point repository, accessed only by the members of the consortium. In this context, the said space can be characterized as private and secure.
- Project internal information: Information gathered from meetings, workshops, and any type of internal communication which will be protected according to each required level of confidentiality. Fruitful and general outcomes of the project will be disseminated without restriction, if no sensitive Data is disclosed. In case of confidential discussions or outcomes access will be granted only to partners that require such for the execution of the project activities assigned to them.
- Research activities: During research that necessitates the collecting of data, the relevant entity will retain and safeguard the data locally. To protect the rights and freedoms of the data subjects, appropriate organizational and technical measures, such as anonymization and/or encryption techniques, will be used. Moreover, open-source data will be collected and will be used as the basis to the project research activities.
- Testing: The Consortium partners will retain and manage data about the testing participants and the processed data. Such testing's results will be reported in an anonymous manner.

Since the present is delivered in an early stage of the project activities, the second version (D7.10) of the Data Management Plan is foreseen to be delivered close to the project end in Month 42 to give a clearer and complete overview of the generated and used data and cover any gaps that exist in the current version.

2.4. SynAir-G Data Description per WP

This section outlines the data produced or processed at each WP and elaborates a number of factors for each of the involved data objects. In the table included in Annex III, each data element is elaborated including the following vital information:

- Short description of data content and type
- Data origin/source (where the data come from)

- Data format & storage
- Confidentiality level (Public, Project Consortium, Data Processor(s))
- Processing/Usage preconditions (restrictions)
- Openness- Reusability
- Related WP /task under which the data is collected

2.5. Type of research results

As included in the GA, the following table provides a description and a classification of the project deliverables categorized as public, or confidential.

No	Deliverable name	Description	Level
1,1	Calibration of low-cost portable pollutant sensors	A number of low-cost portable chemical pollutant sensors will be evaluated and the optimal ones will be calibrated in relation to high-accuracy equipment	PU
1,2	Known and emerging indoor air chemical pollutants	Comprehensive overview of known and emerging indoor air chemical pollutants in classrooms around Europe	PU
1,3	Indoor allergen sensing system	An indoor allergen sensing system with enriched image database & classification algorithm will be developed	PU
1,4	Measures of allergen pollution measures at school	Measures of allergen pollution at school: how much are children exposed	PU
1,5	Virus biosensor prototypes (phase 1-3, n=25)	The first generation of biosensor prototypes for the selected viruses will be developed	SEN
1,6	Virus biosensor prototypes (phase 1-3, n=25)	Improved virus biosensor prototypes, based on feedback on the original prototypes will be developed for piloting in schools	SEN
1,7	Virus biosensor prototypes (phase 1-3, n=25)	The final version of virus biosensor prototypes will be developed for inclusion in the integrated solution	SEN
2,1	Clinical study initiation package	The clinical study will be initiated, including the final protocol and ethical approval from all relevant authorities and study registration number obtained	PU
2,2	Functional sentinel system (wearable/app)	A functional sentinel system, including a wearable and app will be developed	PU
2,3	Midterm recruitment report	Report on the incision of schools, training, baseline assessments and positioning of the sensors	PU
2,4	Health impacts of indoor air pollutants in children	Report on the status of posting health status results from the participants into the registry	PU
2,5	Report on the status of posting results to registry	Health status data will be extracted, cleaned, described, and compared. Relations between the major pollutants and different health outcomes will be assessed. Comparisons between and within subjects, as well as effects of air purification will be evaluated and reported	PU

3,1	Specifications for source identification	The specifications for collecting data for source identification will be reported	PU
3,2	SynAir-G air pollution sources database	A database including school-related indoor air pollutants and their respective sources will be developed	PU
3,3	Indoor/outdoor gradients of air pollutants	Indoor/outdoor gradients of air pollutants will be characterised	PU
3,4	SynAir-G Inhalation Exposure Assessment Tools	A set of tools for assessing pollutant inhalation exposure will be developed	PU
4,1	Pollutant synergy identification in cell models	Pollutant synergy identification in cell models including epithelial and immune cells will be reported	PU
4,2	In-vitro test system of pollutant interactions - PCLS	A model of pollutant exposure based on precision cut lung slices will be developed	PU
4,3	Lung organoid model assessing dose-responses	A lung organoid model assessing synergistic dose-responses will be developed	PU
4,4	Mouse model of complex exposome interactions	Mouse model of complex exposome interactions	PU
5,1	Integrated system requirements specification	The requirements specification for the Integrated system will be collected and analysed	PU
5,2	SynAir-G integrated multi-sensor prototype	SynAir-G validated integrated multi-sensor prototype	SEN
5,3	Eco-friendly indoor air purifier tested	An eco-friendly indoor air purifier will be tested in real-life setting	PU
5,4	Indoor climate improvement device tested	A Biology-based indoor climate improvement device will be tested in a real-life setting	PU
5,5	Functional wireless communications	Wireless communications between the different elements of the SynAir-G devices will be developed, optimised and validated	PU
6,1	Data ingestion engine and data preparation report	The main data ingestion engine will be developed to collect process, integrate and evaluate the data from the different sensors	PU
6,2	Spatiotemporal models of class pollutant dispersion	Spatiotemporal models of classroom pollutant dispersion will be developed	PU
6,3	Report on indoor air pollutant synergies	Results of the AI analysis on indoor air pollutant synergies will be reported	PU
6,4	Cloud based services for IAQ monitoring	Cloud based services for indoor air quality monitoring will be developed	PU
7,1	Communication & dissemination materials	Communication & dissemination materials (website, social media, logo, branding, poster)	PU
7,2	Dissemination and Communication plan	A Dissemination and Communication plan will be developed and reported	PU

7,3	Dissemination Workshop	The outcomes of an external dissemination workshop will be reported	PU
7,4	Guidelines and SynAir-G Position Paper	The Roadmap will be a comprehensive report including training material, published as a white paper with recommendations to authorities, EU policymakers, and the industry. The report will include a compilation of policies, standards, and technologies used in SynAir-G and a selection of best practices	PU
7,5	Guidelines and SynAir-G Position Paper	Guidelines will target healthcare professionals caring for children with allergy & asthma, sensitizing them to the potential risks of indoor air pollution, the synergies with chemical and biological triggers, and potential mitigation measures	PU
7,6	Exploitation Reports	Exploitation Reports	SEN
7,7	Exploitation Reports	Exploitation Reports	SEN
7,8	Report on standardization activities	Report on conducted Standardization activities	PU
7,9	FAIR Data Management Plan (initial & final versions)	FAIR Data Management Plan (initial & final versions)	PU
7.10	FAIR Data Management Plan (initial & final versions)	FAIR Data Management Plan (initial & final versions)	PU
7,11	Final dissemination activities report	Final dissemination activities report	PU
7,12	Website launch	Launch of the project website	PU
8,1	Project management handbook	Project management handbook	PU
8,2	General Assembly Agenda & Report	General Assembly Agenda & Report	SEN
8,3	General Assembly Agenda & Report	General Assembly Agenda & Report	SEN
8,4	General Assembly Agenda & Report	General Assembly Agenda & Report	SEN
8,5	General Assembly Agenda & Report	General Assembly Agenda & Report	SEN
8,6	General Assembly Agenda & Report	General Assembly Agenda & Report	SEN
8,7	Networking workshop	Networking workshop	PU
8,8	Common dissemination and communication activities	Report on common dissemination and communication strategy for the cluster, kick off	PU

		meeting, annual cluster meetings and periodic report of joint activities	
8,9	Cluster web portal and visual identity	Report on cluster web portal and visual identity creation.	PU
8,10	Cluster brochure	Cluster brochure design and development	PU
8,11	Cluster newsletter No.1	Cluster newsletter No.1	PU
8,12	Cluster newsletter No.2	Cluster newsletter No.2	PU
8,13	Shared stakeholder list	Report on shared stakeholder list	SEN
8,14	Shared individual Data Management Plans between cluster partners	Report on shared individual Data Management Plans between cluster partners	PU
8,15	Policy and Scientific Strategy	Report on Policy and Scientific strategy	PU
8,16	Joint policy briefs/factsheets/infographics	Report on joint policy briefs/factsheets/infographics.	PU
8,17	Joint policy briefs/factsheets/infographics	Report on joint policy briefs/factsheets/infographics.	PU
9,1	OEI - Requirement No. 1	Submit the CVs of the members of the Ethics Advisory Board (EAB). The Ethics Advisory Board must be composed by independent experts external to the project, and must report to the funding agency with regard to the ethics issues raised by the project.	SEN
9,2	OEI - Requirement No. 2	1st Ethics Advisory Board report.	SEN
9,3	OEI - Requirement No. 3	2nd Ethics Advisory Board report.	SEN
9,4	OEI - Requirement No. 4	3rd Ethics Advisory Board report.	SEN
9,5	OEI - Requirement No. 5	4th Ethics Advisory Board report.	SEN

3. FAIR Data Management

The Data Management Plan of the SynAir-G project is according to the Guidelines of the EC on FAIR Data Management². In the said document, each project needs to provide the following information:

- How research Data is handled during and after the end of the project;
- Which Data is collected, processed and/or generated;
- Which methodology and standards are applied;
- Whether the Data is shared/made open access, and
- How Data is curated and preserved after the project end.

Beneficiaries that follow the guidelines will ensure that the research Data is findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), as well as ease knowledge discovery and innovation and allow data and knowledge integration and reuse.

Finally, it is important that partners need to use reliable methodologies to ensure that data is backed-up.

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

According to the SynAir-G Grant Agreement section 17, open access to research data is applicable. Thus, the FAIR principle refers to future scientific publications, research results as well as the dissemination material and the digital research data.

According to the same section of the Grant Agreement, regarding the digital research data generated in the action ('data'), the consortium partners, besides the development and update of the current data management plan, must:

(a) deposit data in a trusted research data repository and establish the necessary measures to make it possible for third parties to access, exploit, reproduce and disseminate — free of charge for any user the data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications, as soon as possible; other data, including associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the 'data management plan';

(b) provide information — via the aforementioned repository — about research outputs or any other tool and instrument, at the disposal of the beneficiaries, necessary for validating the project results.

It needs to be noted that open access does not change the obligation to protect results in Article 16 of the Grant Agreement, the confidentiality and security obligations in Article 13 or the obligations to protect personal data in Article 15, all of which still apply.

² http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

In this context and as an exception, partners may not provide open access to specific parts of their research data, in case this harms the legitimate interests of a beneficiary or if the achievement of the action's main objective would be jeopardised by making those specific parts of the research data openly accessible.

It needs to be noted that one of the goals of SynAir-G is related to the findability of the data by making sure that the generated data will be identifiable and easily discoverable.

To this end, and for improving the searchability and enhance the storage in different platforms, project document naming must start with the prefix “[SYNAIR-G]” in order to facilitate quick identification and indexing, as indicated in the table below:

Table 3 Project document naming

Document Type	Types of templates to be used
Deliverables	SYNAIR-G D-No delTITLE_v0.0_date_partner.docx
Agendas	SYNAIR-G meetingID_meetingCITY_meetingDATE_Agenda.docx
Minutes following the organisation of a physical meeting	SYNAIR-G meetingID_meetingCITY_TITLE_meetingDATE_Minutes_v0.0.docx
Minutes following the organisation of a telco	SYNAIR-G Telco ID-ShortTITLE_telcoDATE_Minutes_v0.0.docx
Presentations	SYNAIR-G MeetingID_PPTShortTITLE_meetingDATE_PARTNER.pptx

In this regard, the datasets generated in the scope of the project activities will be accompanied with detailed metadata to improve their discoverability. Where applicable, these metadata will be created in accordance with the OpenAIRE recommendations for Data Archives. The DataCite Metadata Schema v3.1 has been adopted by OpenAIRE, which accepts other persistent identifier schemes in addition to the Digital Object Identifier (DOI), such as the Archival Resource Key (ARK), Handle, Persistent Uniform Resource Locator (PURL), Uniform Resource Name (URN), and Uniform Resource Locator (URL). To ensure discoverability, accessibility, and understandability, non-confidential data obtained throughout the research will be assembled and stored in OpenAIRE's Zenodo repository and/ or IPCHEM platform (see section 3.4 & 6.2).

3.2. Making data accessible

The SynAir-G project outputs as well as the associated deliverables will be accessible to the authorised partners through the project common online collaborative tool (Dropbox). The said space will be organized on WP and Task level following a standardized format.

The public project deliverables will be available in the project’s official website.

Specifically, and in regard to the deliverables that have been defined as ‘Public’ in the Description of Action, a dedicated space will be provided on the project website where they will be uploaded after their review and approval by the EC. Thus, the said reports will be available to all interested parties and stakeholders. Regarding

the deliverables which have been characterized as confidential, meaning that their content is restricted for access only to consortium partners, an executive summary will be available in the project website following the approval EC approval as well.

The project has employed a variety of materials and channels for the enhancement of its footprint as well as for achieving the maximum outreach. This will ensure the reinforcement of the data accessibility. More information regarding the abovementioned can be found in D7.2 Dissemination and Communication plan.

Moreover, and in the scope of maximizing the data accessibility, SYNAIR-G will ensure that project outputs and the related data will be made available using Zenodo (see section 6.2). Zenodo is an open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program operated by CERN which provides researchers the sharing, curation and publication of data and software. The OpenAIRE project was commissioned by the EC to support their nascent Open Data policy by providing a catch-all repository for EC funded research.

Zenodo enables users to make their own collections and decide whether to accept or reject uploaded files. All scientific study results from different sectors can be updated. The user can select from a variety of file formats in the upload form, including journals, posters, presentations, datasets, photos, software, videos/audio, and interactive elements like lessons.

All publicly accessible uploads on Zenodo are given a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to enable quick and easy file citation.

3.3. Making data interoperable

The concept of interoperability describes that both data and metadata produced within the project activities must be machine-readable, that the final document is peer-reviewed and that partners will use a consistent terminology. The SynAir-G partners will observe OpenAIRE guidelines for online interoperability, as included in the following article: <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/>. Partners will also ensure that SynAir-G data observes FAIR data principles under the EC open-access policy: https://enspire.science/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/HE-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf.

In this context, all data will be store as standard formats (e.g., PDF, doc, JSON, etc.). More specifically, the documents and reports created during the course of the project will contain an introductory executive summary, highlighting the contents, target readers, and the expected way to use the document. A README file under the root path including instructions on how to build, execute, and contribute to the code base will be present in every source code repository.

SynAir-G will guarantee that the research data created during the project activity meet the necessary interoperability standards by depositing the project datasets in a data repository compliant with the relevant interoperability guidelines (OpenAIRE's ZENODO) and by providing the necessary metadata description of such datasets as mentioned above. It is also important to note that, changes will be made to metadata vocabularies, standards, and approaches to encourage interoperability.

3.4. Increase data re-use

Modern scientific activity is increasingly characterized by the ability to reuse data. Data re-usability refers to the ease with which one or more research communities (consumer communities) can use data provided by

other research communities for valid scientific research (producer communities). Re-analysis of data, replication and verification of conclusions, reduction of effort duplication, and building on previous work are all made possible by data re-usability.

In this context, SYNAIR-G aims to enable open access to all research data via CC-BY-NC license. However, as it is yet to define in detail which data exactly will be generated and can be made available, this needs to be reevaluated or adapted throughout the project.

The project will ensure that the soonest possible, which datasets will be made available for reuse (for example in the [IPCHEM platform](#)) and under which conditions.

3.5. Data Management Roles & Allocation of Resources

WP7 Project Management is the work package in which the process for data management has been created and will be monitored to ensure compliance with data management decisions as they relate to the DMP. The following summarizes the DMP roles and responsibilities in SynAir-G.

Table 4 Data Management roles and responsibilities

Title	Role	Organisation
WP7 leader	Responsible for preparing the Data Management Plan and policies and providing guidance as necessary.	INLE
Data Controller	Responsible for reviewing the Data Management Plan (DMP) and policies and should be aware of their responsibilities to comply with the GDPR and other applicable regulations.	Each Partner within SynAir-G that is responsible for processing Personal data in accordance with the GDPR.

The costs connected to the FAIR data management have been foreseen and covered by the SynAir-G project budget and in some cases by the partners themselves, since they are part of their internal procedures. In case there are any additional related costs, these will be covered by the respective partner. At the point of submission of the current document, no extra-costs are foreseen.

Table 5 Data Management Costs

Cost Type	Cost Allocation according to DoA
Cost for dataset collection, storage, backup, archiving and sharing that is realized mainly through the Dropbox for project coordination and management	WP1

<p>Costs of storage for data that will be managed locally or on cloud during the solution development, integration and testing (sensor data, cloud platform, wearables data etc.)</p>	<p>Included to WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP6 and more specifically to each partner that is responsible for the system component development and testing.</p> <p>Included under the activities of WP5 “Sensor integration and clean air interventions” and allocated to each partner that is responsible for the respective sensor component to be deployed on the integration platform.</p>
<p>Costs of storage for data that will be managed during the real life testing (app data, wearables, sensors, questionnaire input etc.)</p>	<p>Appointed to WP2 “Real-life multipollutant scenario: children at school and beyond” and to each partner that is responsible for the component to be deployed in real life.</p>
<p>Data management cost for the dissemination and communication activities</p>	<p>WP7</p>

Furthermore, the following human resources have been identified and are covered within the SynAir- G budgeted costs:

- **Data Protection Officer:** According to GDRP each partner will allocate a Data Protection Officer for the collection and any action needed for the handling of personal data. The DPO contact details of each project partner has been collected by INLECOM, as WP7 leader.
- **System Administrators:** That will ensure the uptime, performance, resources and security of the project computers platforms needed for data storage and processing.

It needs to be noted that INLECOM will be the responsible partner for providing guidance in relation to the data management policies. However, each SynAir-G consortium partner will be solely responsible for ensuring that the guidelines listed in the current document are respected.

The dissemination material (e.g., scientific publications) will be made available through OpenAIRE and the project website with no additional costs.

4. Data Security

The SynAir-G consortium partners prioritize the security of the data generated or used during the lifetime of the project. In this context, state-of-the-art technologies will be used for secure storage, delivery and access of information, as well as managing the rights of the users for the data generated or collected. In this way, it will be guaranteed that the accessed, delivered, stored and transmitted content is managed by authorised persons.

The SynAir-G Consortium adopted specific security measures as a set of technological, procedural, and organizational requirements with the goal of implementing an adequate level of security in data processing, to ensure their privacy, availability, and integrity as well as the systems' resilience.

More specifically and regarding personal data, the participants' contact details will be stored in a password protected excel file. The stored data in project's dropbox will not include any personally identifiable information. However, their proper management will be ensured by complying with GDPR and legislation. We will not collect sensitive personal information, such as ethnic origin, political, religious or philosophical beliefs. Where needed, partners will encrypt and anonymize the data to protect personal identities. Most probably, the data anonymization tool 'Amnesia' (OpenAIRE2020) will be used to remove identifying information and diversity and k-anonymity algorithms will be used to ensure anonymity.

Data collected from the cohort will be privacy protected by using one-way hashing encryption and cleaning techniques at the source before uploading them to the cloud, thus eliminating accessible information. In terms of Artificial Intelligence, the algorithms and models will fulfill the ethical guidelines as stated in the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI (published by EC in April 2019) and will follow the current EU guidelines from the AI HLEG reports. The AI system will not include any interaction with humans, and will not pose any risks related to privacy, ethics, human rights, freedoms and biased AI. The system aims to explore synergistic phenomena and identify causal links to improve children's health. In addition, the system will be designed following the transparency-by-design approach by sharing the training datasets in project's public repository and documentation about the system's architecture to produce explainable outcomes.

Specifically, for the storage in the cloud platform, all the information in transit will be performed over secure channels. The use of Transport Layer Security (TLS) with strong ciphers is the established best practice for securing network communication. Additionally, TLS provides integrity and authenticity of the interacting peers. Moreover, the TLS-secured network communication channels and HTTPS will be used both internally (among the platform's components) and externally (when the system is accessed by its users or other systems). The identification and authenticity of the interacting other components will be verified with digital certificates signed by either using well known and trusted Certificate Authorities (CA) or an internal CA of the platform in order to simplify deployment. The latter can facilitate the testing of the components and it's certainly easier, at the cost of supporting only the internal communication. Of use of strong private keys (2048-bit RSA or 256-bit ECDSA), recent versions of TLS, and a short list of strong ciphers that offer at least 128-bit encryption will be utilized.

The outcome of each responsible partner's analysis, evaluation, and risk management process collected led to the selection of the required security measures. The Security processes and tools to be used are described below:

1. **For paper documentation:** filing system for paper documentation, safe storage on office environment, system to destroy paper documentation.
2. **For datasets:** accessing credentials, workstation centralized management system, log management, logical access control and traceability, encryption of data in databases; pseudonymization for some types of data and applications; procedures for destruction of digital data archives.
3. **For systems:** physical access control, firewalls, spyware virus protection, use of secure network protocols, usage of internal network for specific applications, backup and replacement of data storage, use of network protocols and secure applications for data transmission.

4.1. SynAir-G Dropbox

For the internal collaboration among project partners, NKUA is offering a Dropbox account. Below we describe the server capabilities and services as far as physical, network and content security are concerned.

Dropbox³ is designed with multiple layers of protection³, distributed across a scalable, secure infrastructure. These layers of protection include:

- Dropbox applications and infrastructure are regularly tested for security vulnerabilities, and hardened to enhance security and protect against attacks
- Two-step verification is available for an extra layer of security at login
- Public files are only viewable by people who have a link to the file(s)
- Dropbox files at rest are encrypted using 256-bit Advanced Encryption Standard (AES)
- Dropbox uses Secure Sockets Layer (SSL)/Transport Layer Security (TLS) to protect data in transit between Dropbox apps and the company's servers
- SSL/TSL creates a secure tunnel protected by 128-bit or higher Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) encryption

It needs to be noted that for ensuring the confidentiality and protection of information, the cloud server should be hosted in Europe.

4.2. Data confidentiality

Data confidentiality is an overriding concern throughout the SynAir-G project. The confidentiality of the processing, regardless whether it concerns personal or research-related data needs to be warranted throughout the project.

Despite of the fact that it is incorporated into personal data protection or trade secrets treatment, the fact remains that SynAir-G partners need to be concerned, and take concrete measures, towards prohibiting as well, to the best extent possible, unauthorized access to their research (non-personal) data. This is applicable both upon SynAir-G partners that collected the data as well as upon partners that were provided with access or processed data on behalf of others from non-EU or EEA countries.

³ <https://www.dropbox.com/privacy>

In this regard, and in the scope of WP1, an automated particulate sensor will be used to acquire real pollen, mold and dust data and will make replacing used sampling media with fresh easier. The said sensor will be provided to the project from AUTH and the company manufacturer has its premises in the USA. The practical implications of the above are listed below:

1. The entire database (used for the biological aerosol recognition algorithm) will be maybe stored in the company's proprietary cloud in the USA. If that is the case:
2. Data transfer, to and from all partners, will be done through the abovementioned cloud storage.
3. AUTH's access to the data will also be provided through the manufacturer's infrastructure.

AUTH will examine the possibility of transfer the data storage within EU to ensure the data confidentiality throughout the project activities. In case this is not feasible, AUTH, assisted by the Project Coordinator, will sign a Data Transfer Agreement with the manufacturer taking into account the applicable EC guidelines as well as the Data Act and Data Governance Act. The said Agreement will lay down all the principles regarding the data transfer to the cloud platform hosted in the manufacturer's server, including the detailed data flow, the use and ownership of data, the data recovery after the identification process, etc. As the process for the said agreement is still ongoing, more details will be provided in the updated DMP to be delivered in Month 42.

5. Ethical Aspects – Personal Data Protection

Since the solution being built under the auspices of the SYN AIR-G project will be used by children, data confidentiality is a top priority throughout the project and beyond. In light of this, the SynAir-G project is eager to preserve any personal data handled throughout the project's lifespan and will put in place the necessary measures to comply with GDPR requirements. All information to be gathered from project participants will be treated securely, in line with applicable laws governing data protection and privacy, as well as the national ethical standards and requirements. The current document as well as its upcoming version, will describe how sensitive data will be handled, as well as presents the required ethics approvals from the countries where data will be gathered.

With respect to all data processing activities, guidance will be provided by the INLECOM and NKUA that are the leading partners of the associated WP/Tasks and the Independent Ethics Advisors appointed in the project External Advisory Board as well as by the Data Protection Officer of each partner. For partners not having the obligation of appointing a DPO, a GDPR policy has been set in place which is also included in Annex II.

At the time of the drafting of the current document, the personal information that are foreseen to be collected and stored throughout the project duration (as extracted from Table x) are related to:

- Coordination and management purposes (WP8);
- Research activities that involve participants on a voluntary basis, i.e. experiments, questionnaires, interviews, workshops, demonstrations and other testing activities (e.g. as part of WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6);
- Dissemination, communication and exploitation purposes (WP7).

5.1. Coordination and Management

In the context of WP8, the Coordinator and the Task Leaders will process personal data originated from the personnel of the Consortium partners for the purposes of the coordination and management of the project. The data that will be collected are names, email addresses, signatures, voice (during online meetings) and image (if necessary, during online meetings as well). The aforementioned information is obtained directly by the data subjects-researchers themselves.

The purpose of this processing is needed for the performance of the obligations that derive from the SynAir-Grant Agreement as well as the SynAir-G Consortium Agreement.

The storage period is for 5 years after the end of the project according to Data Sheet of the Grant Agreement for accountability reasons towards the EC. Image/voice will be kept for the period necessary for the drafting of minutes.

Only Consortium members will be the recipients of information shared through the project's online repository. Only members who have been given permission can access the repository, which is controlled by NKUA and secured. In case of transfer to the project's non-EU partners will follow Chapter V of the GDPR's rules.

According to the GDPR, the data subjects have certain rights, including the ability to access information, request rectification or erasure of inaccurate data, request a restriction on the use of their personal information, request data portability, and file a complaint with a supervisory authority. Data subjects can exercise these rights by contacting the controller's DPO or, in the absence of a DPO, the controller directly.

The contact details of the Consortium partners' DPOs are available and can be requested by INLECOM. In the case of an absence of a DPO, the contact details of the partners acting as controllers have been used.

5.2. Research activities that involve personal data obtained by the data subjects (volunteers)

The researcher conducting interviews, questionnaires, experiments, collection of health data with volunteers must provide participants with a detailed Information Sheet in advance, in accordance with GDPR outlining the procedures to be followed for the processing of their personal data.

The disclosure of the request for consent shall be made in a manner that is understandable, readily available, and in a plain language. If there are any inquiries when a research activity is being conducted, the researcher will be available to answer and provide clarifications. In order for the researcher/data controller to be certain that the study participants will be able to read the material within at any time and that they will exercise their rights whenever they feel the need to do so, a copy of the Information Sheet will be given to them.

The researcher must first make sure the subject has read and comprehended the information in the information sheet before giving them an informed consent form to process their data. The same applies to the subjects' guardians. If the participant agrees to the data processing, he or she must sign the informed consent form. The same applies for both parents of each study participant. Participants are free to revoke their consent at any time without repercussions.

For the duration specified in the SynAir-G Grant Agreement (5 years following the project's conclusion), the personal information on the Informed Consent Form will be treated in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation and stored securely.

Initiation of the study will be announced to the regulatory bodies and ethics committee. All parents/guardians of eligible participants will be informed about the study during a previously scheduled appointment, and they will receive written information about the study i.e., rationale, aim of the study, the procedures, and possible hazards to which they will be exposed before enrolment into the study. Next to this, they will be informed about the strict confidentiality concerning the acquired medical data. They will be given the opportunity to ask questions and will be informed about the right to withdraw from the study at any time without prejudice. Documented informed consent must be obtained for all participants prior to study inclusion. The informed consent procedure takes place conform the ICH guidelines on Good Clinical Practice. This implies that the written consent form will be signed and personally dated by the participant's legally acceptable representative. The informed consent statement will be signed and dated by the investigator afterwards and participants will receive a copy. The study will be conducted according to the a. principles of the Declaration of Helsinki (Seoul 2008 amendment) and in accordance with the medical Research Involving Human Subjects Act (WMO) and other guidelines, regulations and Acts, b. ICH Harmonized Tripartite Guideline for Good Clinical Practice. The protocol will be approved by the Local, Regional or National Ethics Committees.

Personal identification data (name, date of birth, telephone number and department ID and study IDs) in line with the “personal data definition” according to GCP, will be stored separately and will not be used for analysis. These will be saved in excel locked format, in the coordinator’s and the study centers’ computers and in a locked hard drive separately from other data. Data will be encrypted and processed in an anonymized way throughout the rest of the project activities. The data collected in these interviews will be encrypted with a study number. The data will not identify the participant by name, only by an ID number. The encrypted data will be available to the study center. All data protection laws of the involved countries will be followed. At the end of the study, the analysis of the complete data will be published anonymously and only in summary form, so that no single participant could be identified.

All data generated during the clinical trial will be encrypted and anonymized to protect personal identities, and it will decisively not implement processing algorithms leading to “personally identifying” results. Data collected through the research trials will be privacy protected by using one-way hashing encryption strategies and cleaning techniques at the source before uploading them to the cloud, thus eliminating accessible information. Additionally, it should be noticed that the collected data will not include any personally identifiable information (PII) and their proper management will be ensured by complying with GDPR and local legislation. The project will not collect unnecessary sensitive personal information. Each information sheet will be given a reference number and will not be tied to the subject (person giving the information). The contact details of the participants will be stored in hard copies in a secure place in each research center’s premises and will never be digitalized and uploaded to the web. As stated, during the project, participants will be given the option to withdraw themselves and their data at any time, without consequences. Participants will be given the ability to remain informed about what data is held, collected, and processed.

More information regarding the participation of volunteers in the research activities of the project can be found in the ethics assessment included in the GA and in the Annex II of the current document.

5.3. Dissemination, communication and exploitation of project’s results

The main information source for the project will always be its website. It will be used to disseminate information about the consortium, upcoming events and publications. By including all publicly available material, the website along with the project social media will support dissemination and communication initiatives. To highlight ongoing activities and future planning of the project's activities, SynAir-G will create electronic newsletters and blogposts that are published through the project's web page.

During a meeting or an event, personal information of the participants attending will be collected taken for registration and participation purposes, provided that they have consented to the collection and processing. For this purpose, the registration process will include an Information Sheet for data processing. The storage period is for 5 years after the end of the project according to Data Sheet of the Grant Agreement for accountability reasons towards the EC.

6. Research outputs

Being in line with one of the top aims of the European Commission to expand openness to the research results, as well as to enhance the effectiveness, and reproducibility of research findings, SynAir-G will strongly support the Open Science policy by providing public easy access to information for other relevant public authorities, patient associations, and the general public easy access to information concerning air contaminants, sources, risk factors, and their major sources for pertinent and representative indoor locations and settings.

The project will make its research products—publications, data, software, models, and algorithms—available under open access when possible. The European Open Science Cloud will host the data and articles under the CC BY-NC license. Parallel to this, SynAir-G will create a public repository in ZENODO⁴ to share the obtained monitoring data and the produced scientific data while promoting reusability and adhering to the FAIR Guiding Principles. It needs to be noted that part of the data generated and collected within the project can also be restricted, in case that there is a valid reason to protect the legitimate interest of a partner or an individual. These kinds of dataset will not be made openly available.

In addition, the project will contribute to forums and repositories for indoor air quality sensing, such FAIRMODE and OpenAIRE, and it will give other parties access to the monitoring data through an Open API infrastructure through its cloud services. After receiving EC approval, the project will also deposit its public deliverables on its website and in designated data repositories, and it will take steps to make it easier for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce, and distribute the related materials.

6.1. Open Access to Scientific Publications

It lays into the responsibility of each beneficiary to ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to the project results. In the scope of an EU funded project, open access to scientific publications mainly refers to a free of charge online access for any interested party. Thus, open access will be achieved by implementing the following steps:

1. Any article outlining the project's findings must include the following statement accompanied by the EU emblem: "The research leading to these results has received funding by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101057271 -SynAir-G."
2. Any article or paper, presenting the Action results will be deposited at least by the time of publication to a formal repository for scientific papers. Nevertheless, the paper can be uploaded in the European sponsored repository for scientific papers: <http://zenodo.org/>. It needs to be noted that each case will be examined separately in order to decide whether the self-archiving or paying option will be followed for open access publishing.
3. Authors will make sure that the following will be included in their papers:
 - a. The terms "European Union (EU)" and "Horizon Europe";

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/>

- b. “Disrupting Noxious Synergies of Indoor Air Pollutants and their Impact in Childhood Health and Wellbeing, using Advanced Intelligent Multisensing and Green Interventions”, Grant agreement number 101057271;
- c. Publication data, length of embargo period if applicable; and
- d. A persistent identifier.

6.2. Public repository in ZENODO

In continuation to the information provided in the previous section and to assure adherence to FAIR principles, the consortium has created a repository in ZENODO for the project.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo user interface. At the top, there is a blue header with the Zenodo logo, a search bar, and navigation links for 'Upload' and 'Communities'. A user profile dropdown menu is visible, showing the email 'synairproject@gmail.com'. Below the header, a green notification bar states 'Profile was updated.' The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column contains a 'Settings' sidebar with options: Profile (selected), Change password, Security, Linked accounts, Applications, Shared links, and GitHub. The right column is the 'Profile' editing form, which includes fields for Username (SynAir-G), Full name (SynAir-g EU funded project (GA 101057271)), and Email address (synairproject@gmail.com). A 'Re-enter email address' field is also present. At the bottom of the form are 'Cancel' and 'Update profile' buttons.

Figure 2 SynAir-G ZENODO account

The repository will take into account the following terms, guidelines, and regulations:

- The applicable Task Leader is responsible for gathering the data in the best format possible, store them in the ZENODO repository, and make them searchable.
- All partners must ensure that data sets and research outputs are cross-referencing one another (e.g., publications and the data behind them).
- The description of how to find the data should be included; for example, provide metadata (author, date of publication, etc.)

- Each partner is accountable for their records and documentation related to data generated, which must be in accordance with this DMP and monitored by Task leaders.
- Data will be made accessible within one month of their publication unless the responsible partner has specified justifiable reasons to keep the data confidential.
- Task Leaders should notify the Responsible partner (INLECOM) after uploading data in ZENODO.

7. Conclusions

This Data Management Plan was created to provide project partners with guidance on the requirements and legislation that the project should follow in the delivery of project activities involving data management. This deliverable describes the data that will be created, processed, and used within the SYNAIR-G project and provides specific details on the category and nature of the data involved in each of the SYNAIR-G Work Packages, as well as the SYNAIR-G data's relationship to the project activities.

The report outlines the structured approaches that the SYNAIR-G project will take to ensure that data management adheres to the EC's FAIR data principles. The fifth chapter of this report focuses on ethical aspects and personal data protection based on the current applicable regulation related to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

This deliverable includes all policies that SYNAIR-G will follow to comply with the above as well as the necessary internal processes that SYNAIR-G will follow.

The final version of the DMP will be produced at M42.

Annex I: DMP questionnaire

ID	Data/Metadata Description	Personal Data identification	Data Origin	Data Format	Purpose of data collection	Data sharing - Access	Procedures to safeguard data	Openess - Reusability	Storage	Retention Period
Guidelines	Describe the data/metadata that you foresee to be collected in the project activities your organisation participates.	[Y/N]	Describe the source from which the data/metadata come from.	Describe the format of the data	Analyse the purpose of data collection and relation to project activities -if applicable name the respective task /WP and project objectives	[Internal/External] to the consortium Should access be limited to a specific consortium subgroup? Will any entity (including any service provider) outside of the E.U. have access to these data? If so, who?	Describe any measures/ preconditions for data access and sharing	Potential reuse of data in other domains, work and efforts, studies beyond the project scope -Will you provide open access (publicly available) ? Elaborate how the data can be reused	Please describe where the data will be stored	Please mention the time period for the data retention
examples	Contact details collected for internal communication purposes	y	Public Sources	Spreadsheet, CSV, text	Design & development of project solution...	Internal-Consortium partners with valid justification for processing this dataset	anonysation	Other studies in XY domain		
	Wearable sensor data		Sensors feeds and Services	Percentages, integers, reports as docs and pdfs			encryption	Reference for researchers		
	Personal Data/Health data of participants		Metadata from sources A,B	.json			authentication mechanism	Ledger applications		
			Questionnaires	APIs, .json						

Disrupting Noxious Synergies of Indoor Air Pollutants and their Impact in Childhood Health and Wellbeing using Advanced Intelligent Multi-sensing and Green Interventions

Please provide the contact details of your organization's DPO.

SynAir-G is funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No 101057271. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Annex II: SYNAIR-G GDPR Policy

This Global Data Protection Policy (the “**Policy**”) is drafted by INLECOM with regard to the EU HE Project SYNAIR-G Grant Agreement Number 101057271 (the “**Project**”) executed by the list of partners included in therein (the “**Project Partners**”) in order to:

- Comply with the policy and legal requirements of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation EU 2016/679, the “**GDPR**”), as in effect since 06 June 2020;
- Comply with all other applicable national and EU regulations and guidelines on personal data processing;
- Comply with applicable regulations and best practices with regard to research projects within the EU HE Research Programme;
- Raise awareness and improve knowledge among the Project Coordinator, the Project Partners, as well as their employees and/or agents and/or contractors (collectively, the “**Policy Recipients**”).

Because the field of data protection is a dynamic legal field of constant change, new developments, in the form of new regulations, official reports and/or guidelines, are issued by EU and national legislators, as well as competent national authorities at a constant pace. In this context, this Policy may need to be periodically updated by the Project Coordinator, in order to remain relevant to legislative change. Accordingly, Policy Recipients will be duly informed, and will be asked to provide their renewed consent upon any such updates.

While every effort has been undertaken by the Company to compile a comprehensive, accurate, relevant and lawful Policy, it is expressly clarified that this Policy does not constitute legal advice neither does it warrant compliance to any applicable laws or regulations. This Policy makes no warranties, express or other, on lawfulness, completeness, fitness for a purpose, or merchantability. Recipients and addressees of this Policy are advised to engage legal counsel prior to applying this Policy for their own aims and purposes.

Definitions

For the purposes of this Policy the GDPR definitions, as set in Article 4 of the GDPR, apply. In addition,

“**Personal data**” means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person that is processed by any Project Partner and Policy Recipient during execution of the Project.

“**Controller**” means the owner of the data (usually the creator of the data itself), unless otherwise expressly clarified in this Policy or elsewhere in Project deliverables and/or reports.

“**Processor**” means each Project Partner, unless otherwise expressly clarified in this Policy or elsewhere in Project deliverables and/or reports.

“**Consent**” of the data subject means any freely given, specific, informed, unambiguous and **in writing** indication of the data subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her.

“**Supervisory authority**” means the competent Data Protection Authorities within the Project Partners' jurisdictions.

Aim of the above definitions is to particularise and complement the definitions of Article 4 of the GDPR. Policy Recipients are advised to consult both texts in order to formulate the applicable definitions each time.

Important GDPR provisions

According to **Article 4 par.1 GDPR**, 'personal data' means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.

According to **Recital 26 GDPR**, the principles of data protection should not apply to anonymous information, namely information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or to personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable. Since GDPR does not apply to anonymous information, it is very important to distinguish between anonymised and pseudonymised data, as for the latter GDPR remains applicable.

According to **Article 4 par.7 GDPR**, 'controller' means the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data; where the purposes and means of such processing are determined by Union or Member State law, the controller or the specific criteria for its nomination may be provided for by Union or Member State law.

According to **Article 4 par.8 GDPR**, 'processor' means a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller.

According to **Article 5 par.1-2 GDPR**, the principles relating to the processing of personal data are:

- lawfulness, fairness and transparency;
- purpose limitation;
- data minimisation;
- accuracy;
- storage limitation;
- integrity and confidentiality;
- accountability.

According to **Article 6 par.1 GDPR**, processing shall be lawful only if and to the extent that at least one of the following applies: (a) the data subject has given consent to the processing of his or her personal data for one or more specific purposes; (b) processing is necessary for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party or in order to take steps at the request of the data subject prior to entering into a contract; (c) processing is necessary for compliance with a legal obligation to which the controller is subject; (d) processing is necessary in order to protect the vital interests of the data subject or of another natural person; (e) processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller; (f) processing is necessary for the purposes of the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party, except where such interests are overridden by the interests or fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject which require protection of personal data, in particular where the data subject is a child. Point (f) of the first subparagraph shall not apply to processing carried out by public authorities in the performance of their tasks.

Article 13 GDPR stipulates the information that must be provided by the controller to the data subjects when the personal data is collected by them.

Article 14 GDPR stipulates the information that must be provided by the controller to the data subjects when the personal data is not obtained by them. Paragraph 4 (b) provides for that paragraphs 1 to 3 shall not apply when the provision of such information proves impossible or would involve a disproportionate effort, in particular for processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, subject to the conditions and safeguards referred to in Article 89 par.1 or in so far as the obligation referred to in paragraph 1 of this Article is likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of the objectives of that processing. In such cases the controller shall take appropriate measures to protect the data subject's rights and freedoms and legitimate interests, including making the information publicly available.

Article 25 GDPR stipulates the “Data protection by design and by default”, including procedures for pseudonymisation and data minimisation.

Article 30 GDPR stipulates a “Record of processing activities”, according to which an accurate description of the protection activities shall be kept by the data controller and the data processor and, upon request, made available to supervisory authorities.

Article 32 GDPR stipulates the “Security of processing”. This article aims to ensure that the Data is kept and processed in a secure manner in order to avoid their unlawful or accidental destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure or access. Possible measures to enforce data security include pseudonymisation and encryption as well as regular testing of the implemented technical and organisational measures.

According to **Article 35 par.1 GDPR**, where a type of processing in particular using new technologies, and taking into account the nature, scope, context and purposes of the processing, is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons, the controller shall, prior to the processing, carry out an assessment of the impact of the envisaged processing operations on the protection of personal data. A single assessment may address a set of similar processing operations that present similar high risks.

According to **Article 89 GDPR**, processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, shall be subject to appropriate safeguards, in accordance with GDPR, for the rights and freedoms of the data subject. Those safeguards shall ensure that technical and organisational measures are in place in particular in order to ensure respect for the principle of data minimisation. Those measures may include pseudonymisation provided that those purposes can be fulfilled in that manner.

Policy scope

The Controller determines in advance what is the law applicable to the processing of personal data in a particular case, considering that according to EU law such determination comes from legal principles and cannot be derogated by the parties.

Establishment

Each Project Partner is established on the territory of EU Member States or Affiliated Countries. In the event of any change in establishment, the respective Project Partner shall notify the Project Coordinator duly and in writing.

Unless otherwise expressly specified, each Project Partner is considered the controller in that Member State or Affiliated Country.

Processor outside the EU

In the event of an organization not established on EU territory (such as subsidiaries pertaining to the same corporate group) that processes personal data of people staying on EU territory, on behalf of a Project Partner, that organization qualifies as Processor and ensures the fulfilment of the obligations imposed by the GDPR for that specific part of processing.

Personal data processing

Personal data

Personal data means any information relating to natural persons, that is or can be identified, even indirectly, by reference to any other information including a personal identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.

Special categories of data

Special categories of personal data include data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation as well as the processing of genetic data and biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying an individual.

In the event of such processing the Controller and/or Processor respectively comply with specific rules related to the processing of such data of special categories, as collecting specific informed consent from data subject and applying stricter safeguards.

When the Controller and/or Processor relies on data subject's consent as a legal ground for processing special categories of data, it will meet all legal consent requirements; otherwise, they are only processed if and to the extent it is based on one of the legal grounds listed in the GDPR for the processing of such data.

Data anonymisation

Whenever possible, including non-detrimental to Project execution purposes, Controller and Project Partners shall undertake efforts to keep personal data processed by them for Project purposes anonymous or pseudonymous.

According to the GDPR, “*anonymous information*” is information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person, or personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable. In this context, the GDPR does not apply to the processing of such anonymous information, including for statistical or research purposes.

Similarly, “*pseudonymisation*” means the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal Data is not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person.

Newsletters, social media and other dissemination material

Unless otherwise expressly specified in Project contract, the Controller shall be responsible for the personal data processing carried out for Project dissemination purposes. To this end, the Controller shall:

- Collect and keep all relevant personal data (including lists of contact details), or copies thereof;
- Monitor relevant communications;

- Address to Project Partners instructions and guidelines on Project dissemination activities (including any EU or other state guidelines, whenever available);
- Inform Project Partners of any policy or legal requirements reviews and changes.

Data subjects

Minors

Processing of children's personal data requires a special legitimate basis.

Data processing

Data processing means any operation, or set of operations, carried out with or without the help of electronic or automated means, concerning the collection, recording, organization, keeping, interrogation, elaboration, modification, selection, retrieval, comparison, utilization, interconnection, blocking, communication, dissemination, erasure and destruction of data whether the latter are contained or not in data bank.

Principles for legitimate processing

European Union data protection law set forth the following specific principles which have to be complied with for the processing to be legitimate.

Pertinence and necessity - The Controller should implement management practices to fulfil the obligation to collect only relevant and necessary data for a specified purpose.

Purpose limitation - Personal data is collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a way incompatible with those purposes. The Controller has a clear overview of all purposes for which personal data is processed. Personal data is not processed for purposes besides the original purposes, unless the (secondary) use is compatible.

Data minimization - Personal data collected by the Controller must be adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are collected and further processed; if the same purposes can be realized in a less data intensive way a preference is given to that method.

Data update - Personal data is accurate, and, where necessary, kept up to date. Every reasonable step is taken to ensure that personal data that are inaccurate, having regard to the purposes for which they are processed, are erased or rectified without delay.

Data retention - Personal data is kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal Data is processed. The Controller and/or Processing concerned should have processes and policies in place to:

- 1) determine what the applicable (minimum and maximum) retention periods are for the personal data that is being processed;
- 2) ensure that relevant retention periods are monitored.

The storage period for all data collected or generated in the scope of the project activities is for 5 years after the end of the project (i.e., 31/8/2031) according to Data Sheet of the Grant Agreement for accountability reasons towards the EC.

Data protection legal roles and responsibilities

SynAir-G is funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No 101057271. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

In response to GDPR requirements specific security measures have been implemented in terms of assignment the data protection roles and allocation of data protection legal obligations. As stated in the project GA a Data Protection Officer (DPO) has been appointed and the contact details of the DPO made available to all data subjects involved in the research. Moreover, it has been agreed to consider the whole consortium a “host institution”. It is not foreseen to assign of individual DPOs per partner but whenever required a Data Protection Officer ("DPO") may be designated for assistance in monitoring internal compliance with GDPR.

With regard to the actors involved in personal data processing, the consortium was able to identify the following roles:

Controller

By determining the purposes and means of the processing of personal data, unless otherwise expressly specified in this Policy, the Controller is considered by law as the “Controller” and it is the primary target of the provisions of the law.

Data controller determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data, its key responsibility is to ensure that data collection and processing within the scope of SYN AIR-G, will be carried out in accordance with EU and national legislation. This role will be assumed by the partners data protection officers ("DPOs").

Identification

The data controller previously identifies itself as such and ensures an effective implementation of data protection measures in order to comply with the principle that personal Data is processed fairly and lawfully. The legal role of controller implies specific responsibilities because provisions setting conditions for lawful processing are essentially addressed to the controller.

Accountability

The GDPR provides full accountability of the company/controller regarding the compliance of its processing of personal data with the law. To ensure the effectiveness of that obligation, it prompts the Controller to follow an overall approach, achieving a genuine system of control and management of its pertinent information. So, accountability and compliance system are elements of the framework for the protection of personal data, in the cause/effect relationship: to be compliant and able to prove it (accountability), the Controller needs to put in place a comprehensive compliance system.

Data protection by design

The Controller considers data protection issues from the outset and from the design of the Project, within the whole lifecycle of processing, in order to manage the issues in a proactive way, to reduce costs and improve efficiency.

Data protection by default

The Controller standardizes data protection principles in personal data processing, products and services. The measures adopted ensure that:

- Personal data is processed for purposes not different from the original purposes;
- Only data necessary for these purposes are collected;
- Data is not disclosed without human intervention.

Joint controller

In the event that at any time during Project execution the Controller processes personal data in conjunction with a third party, by jointly determining the purposes and means of the processing, they both act as joint controller. Both joint controllers determine the mutual responsibilities with a specific arrangement.

Processor

Unless otherwise specified expressly in this Policy, all SYN AIR-G partners handling personal Data is considered as Data Processors, meaning that they process personal data under the control and guidance by the Data Controller.

A processor processes personal data on behalf of the Controller – that is, the Controller delegates all or part of the processing activities to them. In such event the Project contract assumes the role of the relevant required written agreement as per GDPR requirements.

The processor warrants that it shall provide sufficient guarantees to ensure compliance with the GDPR, has implemented appropriate controls to meet data protection requirements defined by the agreement, instructions and/or legal requirements and ensures the protection of the rights of data subjects.

Auditing

The Controller ensures the commitment of the Processor(s) to enable and contribute to any review activities, including inspections, carried out by the Controller or other (EU authorities') auditors and/or reviewers, as appropriate.

Security

Each Project Partner undertakes that it adopts appropriate security measures to ensure the security, integrity and confidentiality of personal information and electronic communications at an adequate level with regard to Project purposes, and at any event at no lower level than processing of similar data within its own organisation.

Identification

Each Processor appoints a DPO in accordance with the criteria and the requirements set forth in the GDPR, as applicable to it. In such event, it shall notify the Controller in writing accordingly.

Designation compulsory vs. voluntary

Each Processor documents the reasons supporting the designation of the DPO or, rather, the reasons why such designation is deemed not necessary. This documentation forms part of the data protection documentation system of that Processor.

Professional requirements

The DPO has sufficient authority, professional qualities and independence to ensure success in his role, according to the GDPR provisions.

Tasks

The organization assigns to the DPO at least the tasks listed in the GDPR.

Notification to Supervisory Authority

Whenever a DPO is appointed the organization notifies the Supervisory Authority of such designation and publishes DPO's contact details.

People in charge of processing

Individuals who process personal data under the authority of the Controllers or Processor(s) must receive specific formal instructions. Hence, the Controller gives specific instructions, relating also to the implementation of security measures and safeguards, to all of its personnel in charge of processing personal data.

Training and awareness

All Project Partners' employees should be well informed and aware of data protection implications and be able to carry out their obligations in their work. A data protection education and communication program should be in place and supported by a monitoring system that confirms all employees and/or contractors are appropriately trained on their data protection responsibilities.

Policies and procedures

Data protection policies and procedures exist, are documented in writing, are formally approved by management, implemented, reviewed, updated and approved when there are changes to applicable laws and regulations.

All Project Partners understand, and the Controller may ask them to overview all their personal data processing, the data protection risks and the applicable rules and procedures. In such event, they shall provide it with all requested information to the best of their ability without undue delay.

Notice and consent

Notice

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, provides the information required by law to the data subject in a concise, transparent, intelligible and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language, in particular for any information addressed specifically to a child.

The data protection notice informs data subjects about the processing of personal data relating to them, even when the personal data is not collected from them as well as of their rights, in order to let them verify in particular the accuracy of the data and the lawfulness of the processing.

Free and informed consent

Personal data is processed if and to the extent that the data subject has given valid consent to the processing for one or more specific purposes, or another legal basis for processing exists.

Systems or applications are able to document the explicit consent of the data subject so that it can be evidenced at any time.

Other legal grounds for a legitimate personal data processing are the following:

1. performance of a contract;
2. legal obligation;
3. vital interest of data subject;
4. public interest;

5. legitimate interest of the controller or third party.

If "legitimate interest" is used as a basis, the interests that have preceded to the decision, need to be documented as well as any possible mitigating measures which will be taken to be able to proceed with personal data processing based on the defined interests.

Withdrawal of consent

Data subject's consent can be withdrawn at any time; even though it will not affect the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal.

Rights of data subjects

The individual whom the data refers to (data subject) is entitled with specific rights set forth by the law. The GDPR requires that each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, must facilitate the exercise of the data subject's rights, take action on the request within a specific time frame and must communicate the information requested in an intelligible and easy to access form.

- Right of access

Any individual must be able to exercise the right of access to data relating to him which are being processed.

- Right to rectification

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should have a procedure in place for data subjects to request rectification of their personal data. The procedure specifies in which cases rectification is legitimate. If a data subject's request for rectification is legitimate, this is executed across all relevant data storage facilities, including those managed by third parties.

- Right to erasure

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should have a procedure in place for data subjects to request erasure of their personal data. The procedure specifies in which cases erasure is legitimate. If a data subject's request for erasure is legitimate, this is executed across all relevant data storage facilities, including those managed by third parties.

- Right to restriction of processing

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should have a procedure in place for data subjects to request restriction of processing of their personal data. The procedure specifies in which cases restriction is legitimate. If a data subject's request for restriction of processing is legitimate, this is executed across all relevant data storage facilities, including those managed by third parties.

- Right to data portability

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, determines which processes are subject to the right of data portability as well as when the requirements for such right are met.

Data subject can request the organization to receive a machine-readable copy of the personal data the organization holds about them and where possible, enable the transfer of this data to another data controller.

Portability right can be exercised when:

1. Processing operations are based on data subject's consent or on contract;

2. Personal data concerns the data subject and are the same that the latter has provided to the organization;
3. The right does not adversely affect rights and freedoms of others;
4. The processing is carried out by automated means.

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, implements appropriate measures and procedures to provide data subject, who is entitled to, with a structured, commonly used and machine-readable copy of the personal data it holds about him and where possible, to enable the transfer of this data to another data controller indicated by data subject.

- Right to object

Where personal Data is processed for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, the data subjects have the right to object on grounds relating to their particular situation (unless the processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out for reasons of public interest). The right to object is explicitly brought to the attention of the data subject at the latest at the time of the first communication with the data subject, presented clearly and separately from any other information. Measures should be in place to assess such objections and to ensure that such processing ceases when the request is legitimate and needs to be respected.

Data subjects have right to object, on request and free of charge, to the processing of personal data relating to them for purposes of direct marketing.

- Automated decision making

Data subject has the right to object to any automatic decision-making (including profiling).

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, will have determined which processes entail automated decision-making (including profiling) and will have established measures to allow data subjects to object to such automated decision making and profiling. Suitable measures are in place to safeguard the data subject's rights and freedoms and legitimate interest, at least the right to obtain human intervention on the part of the Company/controller, to express his or her point of view and to contest the decision.

- Timely response to exercise of rights

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, must confirm to data subjects without delay whether data relating to them are processed and communicate the data to them in an intelligible form. Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should implement internal procedures in order to be able to provide a timely response to the requests of data subject for the exercise of his rights.

Measures have to be implemented in a way that effectively allows an individual to exercise his or her right to personal data, and that enables Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, to respond to such request appropriately within the required timeframes.

Notification to recipients

In case of a legitimate exercise of rights to rectification, erasure or restriction of processing recipients of the personal data should be informed of the rectification, erasure of that data or of the restriction of processing.

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should have a procedure in place for communicating any rectification or erasure of personal data or restriction of processing to the recipients to whom the personal data has been disclosed and for disclosing these recipients to the data subject, if so requested.

Data protection documentation system

Register of processing

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, with regard to their processing activities must set up a relevant record, maintained in writing (including in electronic form) and made available easily and swiftly to the supervisory authority on request, as per applicable legal requirements within their respective Member States. The record of processing activities shall contain all the information required by GDPR.

Consequently, the Controller shall have an up-to-date overview of all personal data processing activities and shall maintain records within the Project, that meet the legal requirements posed by the GDPR. By so doing, the Controller will be able to demonstrate compliance to any Supervisory Authority or other state or EU authority concerned.

For the avoidance of doubt, each Project Partner carries the same responsibility above within its own respective organisation.

Register of data breaches

A specific register where the breaches have to be recorded together with other information specified by the law, must be maintained by the Controller and shown to the Supervisory Authority upon request. This register is an important element of the data protection documentation system.

Project Partners need to notify immediately and in writing the Controller of any personal data breach within their respective organisations that affects execution of the Project in any way, and to cooperate with the Controller while applying relevant GDPR legal requirements.

Data protection assessment

Assessment

In the event that a Data Protection Impact Assessment (“**DPIA**”) is carried out under the Project, the Controller shall ensure that personal data receives the appropriate level of protection in accordance with the assessed data protection risk.

The decision whether to carry out a DPIA under the Project, unless undertaken in respective Project contract, will be made by the Controller upon prior written consultation with the Project Partners.

Adequacy of protection

The Controller, assisted by Project Partners, should have a process in place in order to assess for all processing the risks of varying likelihood and severity for the rights and freedoms of natural persons, taking into account the nature, scope, context and purposes of personal data processing.

Impact assessment in case of high risk (DPIA)

When the preliminary assessment highlights that processing represents high risks, a formal and documented DPIA is carried out by ascertaining possible impact on data subject.

DPIA is conducted in such a way to meet all the requirements set forth by the GDPR (art. 35) in order to confirm the quality and validity of the findings.

Prior consultation to Supervisory Authority

The Controller has a process in place and roles are assigned in order to ensure that when a DPIA determines that the processing represents high risks, the competent Supervisory Authority is consulted prior to the processing.

Technical and organizational measures

The Controller and each Project Partner, as appropriate, adopts appropriate technical and organisational measures with regard to Project execution (the “**Measures**”), and reviews and updates them where necessary, to ensure and to be able to demonstrate that processing is in compliance with GDPR.

Each Project Partner shall notify relevant Measures to the Controller in writing. In the event of any queries or further requests by the Controller, each Project Partner undertakes to address them duly and in writing.

In the event that any Project Partner has notified the Measures to its competent Supervisory Authority, it shall inform the Controller thereof, and shall provide respective copies thereof.

Data breach

According to GDPR, the Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, has to implement adequate Measures in order to prevent personal data breaches.

In addition, the Measures should be able to minimize the adverse effects, in case a security breach to personal data relating in any manner to the Project occurs anyhow.

Should a data breach occur, GDPR sets forth that the Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, has to notify it to the Supervisory Authority providing specific information, without undue delay and in any case no later than 72 hours from the time of knowledge.

When the breach leads to significant risk of serious adverse effects on the data subject(s) or serious adverse consequences for the protection of personal data, also the latter must be informed without undue delay.

Data transfers to third countries

No international transfers of personal Data are expected to take place under the Project.

In the event that any Project Partner wishes to carry out such personal data processing, it shall notify the Controller in writing and in advance. Unless otherwise expressly specified, any international data transfers carried out by any Project Partner for any reason during Project execution take place at its own exclusive liability and responsibility; same Project Partner shall hold all other Project Partners (including the Controller) harmless from any legal or other claims arising for such personal data processing.

Sanctions and damages

In case of violation of data protection principles and rules, each Project Partner (including the Controller) is responsible for damages and is subject to sanctions. Possible violations may involve civil liability and sanctions in order to ensure that any relevant damage is compensated.

The Project Partner (including the Controller) that is liable for said damages and/or sanctions shall hold all other Project Partners harmless from any claims, costs, and expenses arising from relevant GDPR infringement.

SYNAIR-G Day-to-Day Data Usage and Related Processes

In direct connection of what included in current document, SYNAIR-G recognises the need for creating some process related policies so that there is overall agreement of the usage/storage/retention/opt-out etc. of

data from every-day (day-to-day) project activities. A list of such matters is included below where the means that the consortium will tackle them reflects the whole consortium agreed approach.

SYNAIR-G list of Project Advisory Board Contacts

The SYNAIR-G list of Project Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board (SEAB) contacts relates to an excel sheet that includes the names of all the AB Members and their email addresses. It also indicates their expertise (justifying the purpose of contacting each of them) along with the organisation they belong. Only the coordinator and relevant consortium partners have access to this list of contacts. The purpose of this list is to keep a well organised list of Project SEAB contacts for the SYNAIR-G communications. The data will be erased after the project end and not kept or maintained after the project end. This list is being stored at the SYNAIR-G Dropbox document server. Any person has the right to opt out of this list by direct email to the project coordinator.

Meetings' related material

This relates to any document created and used for the purposes of project meetings. These may relate to agendas, presentations, minutes, signature lists or any other internal document created for the purposes of SYNAIR-G meetings. All these documents will be created and maintained for internal purposes of SYNAIR-G and only SYNAIR-G partners will have access to them at the SYNAIR-G Dropbox under the meetings section. They will be kept for 5 years after the project end (for auditing reasons). Any person has the right to opt out of being mentioned in these by direct email to the project coordinator before or after the meeting.

Workshops/Conferences and Training sessions

These data relate to the creation of workshops, agendas, programmes, participants' lists etc and in general dissemination material related to SYNAIR-G organised workshops. Regarding the external publication of this material, we consider that this material can be fully anonymized so that it excludes personal information from the presenters/participants in the related programmes/agendas that will be shared publicly. For the parts of the related material that will be used for the workshop organisation internally to SYNAIR-G, the related files will be stored in the Dropbox server under the section meetings. The data will be kept for 5 years after the project end for auditing reasons. Any person has the right to opt out of being mentioned in these by direct email to the project coordinator before or after the event.

Reporting

Reporting refers to internal and external (EC) documents including SYNAIR-G progress of activities, technical overviews etc. Related files will be including documents (reports with no personal identifiable information) and financial data (C forms) sometimes including personal data. The purpose of these data is financial so that partners can claim budget requests for their related effort in SYNAIR-G. C forms will be maintained by the project coordinator only and stored at internal and secure server. These (per partner) Data is not to be shared with anyone internally or externally to SYNAIR-G, will be kept for 5 years after the project end (for audit purposes) and will be deleted after this date. Opting out of these data will be possible but will require an updated Form C to be submitted by the project partner.

Deliverables, internal documents and other SYNAIR-G reports

During the SYNAIR-G project run-time, a large series of documentation and reporting will be provided relating to the project deliverables and/or internal documents etc. These files will be used for the project contractual obligations and shared to: SYNAIR-G partners, EC, everyone (depending on deliverable type). In these documents, the name of authors will be included. Following this, as far as the internal (to SYNAIR-G)

and EC distributed documents are related, they will be used only for the purposes of reporting and stored in the SYNAIR-G Dropbox under the deliverables section. Reports that will be shared publicly (public deliverables) will mention only the partner's name and not any other personal information. All reports will be kept for 5 years after the project end for auditing reasons.

Source codes

As far as the inclusion of personal information inside source codes is concerned, SYNAIR-G intends to not use any such information into actual source code files produced in the framework of SYNAIR-G foreground. In case that any partner wishes to include any personal information, a related consent form will have to be created, used and signed by the data owner(s).

Usage of cookies (in SYNAIR-G sites)

In the cases that in a SYNAIR-G application (web) the usage of cookies is needed, a related pop-up window informing the user must be present, prompting the user to accept (or not) the conditions under which her/his personal information are stored. SYNAIR-G will maximize efforts to reduce the usage of cookies in its web developments.

Lists of stakeholders and SYNAIR-G contacts

This list refers to internal to SYNAIR-G lists of external stakeholders including potential technology/results up-takers, major links with end-users and other stakeholders. This list will be used for communication purposes of SYNAIR-G, no external access will be allowed (restricted to SYNAIR-G partners) and will be stored in the SYNAIR-G Dropbox. When people are being registered to this list, a consent by email will have to be sent by the data owner. The data will be kept until the SYNAIR-G end. Any person has the right to opt out of being mentioned in these by direct email to the project coordinator.

Project related research data (data from testing and research activities)

Any data circulated internally to SYNAIR-G for research purposes must be fully anonymized by the data owner (in this case the data controller) and not relating in any case to personal information as stated in the sections above.

Any other SYNAIR-G related data

In case that personal information needs to be added in any other document in SYNAIR-G, the controller (document creator) will have to notify the data owners of their personal details being included into the related document, purpose, retention, storage etc.

Summary of data that fall under GDPR special treatment have been included in Annex III along with the procedures for their protection.

Annex III: SYNAIR-G Data Description

Dataset Description	Type	Format	Storage	Related WP/Project activity	Partners	Openess - Reusability	Procedures to safeguard data	Data sharing - Access
Literature	Electronic document	Word (.doc/.docx)	Dropbox	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	ALL	Reference for researchers	N/A	Internal / External to the Consortium
		Pdf						
References	Electronic document	Endnote database (.enl)	Dropbox	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	ALL	Reference for researchers	N/A	Internal / External to the Consortium
		Word (.doc/.docx)						
Images	Electronic Document	TIFF, JPEG, PNG, JPEG/JFIF, GIF etc.	Dropbox	All WPs	NKUA,EFA	N/A	Consent form from participants and storage only for the	Internal to the Consortium with consent form. In case

Audio Files	Electronic Document	WAVE, AIFF, MP3, MXF, FLAC etc.	Dropbox	All WPs	NKUA, EFA	N/A	necessary retention period.	the dataset will be made available external to the Cosnortium , consent from the subjects will be granted.
Video Files	Electronic Document	MOV, MPEG-4, AVI, MXF etc.	Dropbox	All WPs	NKUA, EFA	N/A		
Deliverable	Electronic Document	Word (.doc/.docx)	Dropbox	All WPs	ALL	Only public deliverables will be made available to the project website and Cordis	No personal information will be included	Internal / External to the Consortium
		Excel (.xls/.xlsx)	Dropbox					
		Pdf	Dropbox					
Software	Code	Several Programme Languages	Locally	WP2, WP6	UoP, INLE, CYRIC	To be examined on a case by case basis	N/A	Internal to the Consortium
Human lung tissue PCLS	Experiments read out	CSV, xlsx, text, fcs, czi, jpeg	Locally in partners servers	Task 4.2, 4.3	UKER, SIAF	Access after publication for similar research interest	authentication mechanism, Anonymisation	Internal- Consortium partners with valid justification for processing this dataset

Cell culture cell lines experiment outcomes	Experiments read out	CSV, xlsx, text, fcs, czi, jpeg	Locally in partners servers	Taks 4.1.	NKUA, UER	Access after publication for similar research interest	n/a	Internal-Consortium partners with valid justification for processing this dataset
Cell culture experiments with human primary cells	Experiments read out	CSV, xlsx, text, fcs, czi, jpeg	Locally in partners servers	Taks 4.1.	NKUA, UER	Access after publication for similar research interest	authentication mechanism, Anonymisation	Internal-Consortium partners with valid justification for processing this dataset
Air pollutant (chemical and biological) sensor data from classrooms	Sensors	Spreadsheet and text files, TIFF, JPEG, PNG, JPEG/JFIF, GIF etc.	UoP Cloud (exception is the sensor provided by AUTH, where the data will be stored to the manufacturer's cloud)	Automated, real-time sensing of multiple environmental exposures WP1 - WP5	CYRIC, NAAVA, FORTH,TE QOYA, EPFL, AUTH ,CNR	Access after publication for similar research interest	N/A	Internal / External to the Consortium
Accurate air pollutant measurements from classrooms	Accurate instruments	Spreadsheet and text files	UoP server / Locally	Automated, real-time sensing of multiple environmental exposures WP1&WP5, Non-automated measurement of multiple environmental	CYRIC, NAAVA, FORTH,TE QOYA, EPFL, AUTH ,CNR	Access after publication for similar research interest	N/A	Internal / External to the Consortium

				Exposures WP1&WP5				
Assessment of the cytotoxicity of pollutants.	Experiments read out (Airway organoid culture, Airway-on-a-chip culture)	Spreadsheet (xlsx), Figure (tif), Video (avi), Text (doc)	Locally in partners servers	Task 4.3	SIAF	Reference for researchers for works in the air quality and pollution domain through papers. The dataset will not be publicly available.	N/A	Internal-Consortium partners with valid justification for processing this dataset
Assessment of the effect of pollutants on airway epithelial barrier function.								
Assessment of inflammatory properties of pollutants.								
Assessment of synergistic effects to pollutants.								
Cell culture murine primary cells and cell lines	Experiments read out	CSV, xlsx, text, fcs, czi, jpeg	Locally in partners servers	Task 4.4.	UKER	Access after publication for similar research interest	n/a	Internal-Consortium partners with valid justification for processing this dataset

Murine experiment of asthma	Experiments read out	CSV, xlsx, text, fcs, czi, jpeg	Locally in partners servers	Task 4.4.	UKER	Access after publication for similar research interest	n/a	Internal-Consortium partners with valid justification for processing this dataset
Environmental data	Questionnaires/public sources	APIs, .json	Locally	To understand and evaluate the impact of the environment on health data collected from children	NKUA, CHUM, UOULU,CA IR, UMAN, UKER	Access after publication for similar research interest	n/a	Internal to the Consortium
Socioeconomic data	Game app/public sources	Exported File, API	Locally	To set-up a cohort of children from different socioeconomic origins in order to evaluate the impact of the socioeconomic factors on health data collected from children	NKUA, CHUM, UOULU,CA IR, UMAN, UKER	Access after publication for similar research interest	anonymization with specific id for the project will be stored separately and will not be used for analysis. These will be saved in excel locked format, in the Coordinator's personal computer and in a locked hard drive in the Coordinator's office, separately from other data.	Internal to the Consortium

Partners' contact details	Electronic document	xls	Dropbox	All WPs - Internal communication purposes	NKUA	N/A	According to the GA, partners will have access to contact details for the purposes of the project	Internal-Consortium partners with valid justification for processing this dataset
Testing participants contact details	Electronic document	CSV, text , xls	Locally in research institutes	To establish the Children cohort - WP2	NKUA, CHUM, UOULU,CA IR, UMAN, UKER	No openness/ reusability	anonymization with specific id for the project will be stored separately and will not be used for analysis. These will be saved in excel locked format, in the Coordinator's personal computer and in a locked hard drive in the Coordinator's office, separately from other data.	Study Corodinator and WP2 leaders
	Hard copy document (signed)	hard-copies (inform consents)		To establish the Children cohort - WP2				
Wearable sensor data	Sensors feeds & services	Percentages, integers, reports as xls, doc, pdf or csv.	UoP server	WP6, Tasks 2.2, 2.4, 2.5, Design & development of the SynAir-G Inhalation Exposure Assessment Tools (WP3)	UoP, NKUA, CHUM, UOULU,CA IR, UMAN, UKER,INLE	Reference for researchers for works in the air quality and pollution domain through papers. The dataset will not be publicly available.	Anonymization with specific id for the project will be stored separately and will not be used for analysis. These will be saved in excel locked format, in the Coordinator's personal computer and in a locked hard drive in the	Internal to the Consortium

							Coordinator's office, separately from other data. Encryption	
Participants' data collected at school (health and exposure data)	Paper questionnaires/ reports of measures (height-weight), respiratory tests results (spirometry) and samplings results (urine, blood (option))	CSV, text, hard-copies	In the SynAir-G database (UoP server) & locally in a PC protected with a password and in a locked hard drive in the study center	To evaluate and understand the impact of indoor pollutants on children health (WP2, WP3)	NKUA, CHUM, UOULU, CA IR, UMAN, UKER	No openness/ reusability	Anonymization with specific id for the project will be stored separately and will not be used for analysis. These will be saved in excel locked format, in the Coordinator's personal computer and in a locked hard drive in the Coordinator's office, separately from other data.	Study Corodinator and WP2 leaders
	Electronic Questionnaires	CSV, text , xls						
Health data of asthmatic participants collected at the hospital	Electronic patients' file (DxCare Software)	CSV, text , xls, .pdf						
Health data of participants	Questionnaires about health history, current health status, comorbidities	hard copies, database excel and, weblink, online questionnaires	In the SynAir-G database (UoP server) & locally in a PC protected with a password and in a locked hard drive in the study center	Tasks 2.1, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5	NKUA, CHUM, UOULU, CA IR, UMAN, UKER	Reference for researchers for works in the air quality and pollution domain through papers. The dataset will not be publicly available.	Anonymasation, Authentication mechanisms -locally in the SynAir-G database (hosted in UoP server) and in a locked hard drive in the study center	Whole Consortium
		Game app	UoP server					

	lung function and airway inflammation	SynAir-G database and exported excel file	In the SynAir-G database (hosted in UoP server) & locally in a PC protected with a password and in a locked hard drive in the study center	Tasks 2.1, 2.5				
	Blood, urine and shophrayngeal samples	SynAir-G database and exported excel file	In the SynAir-G database (UoP server) & locally in a PC protected with a password and in a locked hard drive in the study center	Tasks 2.1, 2.5				
	Height- weight measurements	Hard copies (if needed) stored securely in the research cetners , SynAir-G database (hosted in the UoP server) and exported excel file	In the SynAir-G database (UoP server) & locally in a PC protected with a password and in a locked hard drive in the study center	Tasks 2.1, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5				

